

THE ROLE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP SKILLS TO DEVELOP ENTREPRENEURIAL TALENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

This study analyses the factors that influence the development of students' entrepreneurial talents in higher education, focusing on the role of curriculum content, teaching style, and entrepreneurial skills. Although entrepreneurship education has been widely implemented, there is still a gap between the implementation of education and students' success in entrepreneurship. This study uses a qualitative and quantitative approach and takes 300 students from Indonesia and Malaysia who take entrepreneurship courses as respondents in this study. Interviews were also conducted with entrepreneurship lecturers. Data analysis uses SEM-PLS to test the relationship between variables. The results of the survey indicate that curriculum content has a positive and significant influence on entrepreneurial skills (0.452; $p < 0.001$) and entrepreneurial talent development (0.369; $p < 0.001$). Entrepreneurial skills significantly influence talent development (0.468; $p < 0.001$). However, teaching style did not show a significant influence. Entrepreneurial skills proved to be an effective mediator between curriculum content and talent development (mediation coefficient = 0.212; $p < 0.001$). The conclusion drawn in this study states that curriculum content is the most crucial factor in developing entrepreneurial talent, with "what is taught" being more important than "how to teach it". The recommendations given as managerial implications in this study are aimed at educational institutions, focusing more on developing quality entrepreneurship curricula and transforming entrepreneurship teaching to be more attractive to students.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education, Entrepreneurial Talent, Entrepreneurial Skills, Curriculum Content, Higher Education.

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship education has received special attention from the government and educational institutions in recent years. Entrepreneurship education has begun to be provided from elementary to higher education levels as early as possible. The application of entrepreneurship education at the elementary level differs from that at higher education levels. Still, it has the same goal: building knowledge and entrepreneurial talent for students. Both elementary and higher education institutions have worked hard to prepare students to have the ability to face the challenges that will arise in the modern business world today. Therefore, entrepreneurship education is essential in education, especially in higher education. Entrepreneurship education in higher education aims to equip students with the skills and knowledge needed to win the competition in an increasingly competitive business world successfully.

Previous research by William and Linda (2023) stated that entrepreneurship education based on Christian missions in the Faculty of Theology is essential to develop. The goal is to hone

the skills and talents of students so that they can become entrepreneurs to help the economy in their studies. The development of entrepreneurship education also needs to be carried out at universities in the ASEAN region, focusing on learning technical skills, entrepreneurial skills, and shaping students' maturity. The development that has been carried out so far has not been successful in turning students into entrepreneurs. This failure arises because students are not encouraged to carry out the business development they have done while studying. The results of other studies related to methods in entrepreneurship education conducted by Setyoningrum *et al.* 2023 revealed that classroom learning methods and additional activity methods have a direct positive effect on entrepreneurial intention, with an indirect impact given by attitudes towards entrepreneurship and perceived behavioral control. The results of this study explain that although the two teaching methods' direct effects are similar, using the additional activity method can effectively improve attitudes towards entrepreneurship and perceived behavioral control, which can positively impact entrepreneurial intention more broadly. The opinions of Jocelin and Ida (2022) and Kusumajanto (2017) show that entrepreneurship education has a positive and significant effect on entrepreneurial intention, entrepreneurial attitudes, and entrepreneurial intention.

Although entrepreneurship education that focuses on developing technical and entrepreneurial skills in college has been widely implemented (not only as a science studied by students in social science study programs), the results of this learning have not been fully optimal in creating new entrepreneurs from college graduates. Several studies show a gap between implementing entrepreneurship education and students' success in entrepreneurship. Students who are genuinely successful in developing a business are usually so because they have a background of parents or families who also have businesses. In reality, many students still develop enterprises only as a college assignment. The teaching method in the classroom that may be less interesting is a serious question that needs to be answered regarding what approach is most effective in transforming knowledge and skills in entrepreneurship education in college. Another question is what factors can influence the development of entrepreneurial talent in students to be born as successful entrepreneurs eventually.

Based on the existing background, the objectives of this study are to: 1. Analyze the factors that influence the development of students' entrepreneurial talents in higher education. 2. Analyze the teaching style of entrepreneurship lecturers in developing students' entrepreneurial talents in higher education, 3. Identify the obstacles experienced by students in developing businesses developed during and after college 4. Provide strategic recommendations to increase the influence of entrepreneurship education on the development of students' entrepreneurial talents.

METHOD

The research methodology is designed to answer the research objectives on developing students' entrepreneurial talents in higher education. This study uses two research methods, namely qualitative and quantitative approaches. Both methods ensure a comprehensive analysis of the various factors that influence entrepreneurship education in higher education.

The data used in this study were obtained through a survey. Respondents in this study were students who were or had taken entrepreneurship courses in all Faculties at one of the PTS in the Jakarta area (representing Indonesia) and at one of the State Universities in Malaysia. The sample used in this study was 300 students, divided into 200 students from Indonesia and 100 from Malaysia. In addition to using questionnaires distributed to students, the interview method was also used in this study. Interviews were conducted with six entrepreneurship lecturers at universities in Indonesia and Malaysia to find out what methodologies were used by lecturers in teaching entrepreneurship in class. The following is a conceptual research model and the hypothesis formed from this model:

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

The following is the proposed research hypothesis:

- H1: Teaching Style Has a Direct Positive Influence on the Formation of Entrepreneurship Skill.
- H2: Curriculum Content Has a Direct and Positive Influence on the Formation of Entrepreneurship Skills.
- H3: Teaching Style Has a Direct Positive Influence on the Formation of Entrepreneurship Talent.
- H4: Curriculum Content Has a Direct and Positive Influence on the Formation of Entrepreneurship Talent.
- H5: Entrepreneurship Skills Have a Direct and Positive Influence on the Formation of Entrepreneurial Talents
- H6: The impact of teaching style on entrepreneurial talents is moderated by Entrepreneurship Skill
- H7: The impact of Curriculum Content on entrepreneurial talents is moderated by Entrepreneurship Skill

Table 1: Indicator Variables

No.	Variables	Indicator	Reference
1.	Teaching Style	Experiential Learning	Heinze, A. (2020), "How Entrepreneurship Can Be Learned through Experiential Learning Formats, Especially through Training Firms", <i>International Journal of Management and Applied Research</i> , Vol. 7, No. 4, pp. 471-481. https://doi.org/10.18646/2056.74.20-033
		Interactive Teaching Methods	
		Feedback Mechanisms	
2.	Curriculum Content	Business Planning Skills	Rodrigues, A. L. (2023). Entrepreneurship Education Pedagogical Approaches in Higher Education. <i>Education Sciences</i> , 13(9), 940. https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13090940
		Marketing and Sales Strategies	
		Financial Management	
		Risk Management	
3.	Entrepreneurial Skills	Strategic Thinking	Catherine Cote, Harvard Business School, 2020
		Leadership Skills	
		Problem-Solving	
		Adaptability	
		Idea Generation	
		Product Development	
4.	Entrepreneurial Talent Development	Attitudes Towards Entrepreneurship	Jardim, J. Entrepreneurial Skills to Be Successful in the Global and Digital World: Proposal for a Frame of Reference for Entrepreneurial Education. <i>Educ. Sci.</i> 2021, 11, 356. https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci110703
		Self-Efficacy	
		Perceived Behavioral Control	
		Entrepreneurial Readiness	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following is an explanation of the research results based on the answers given by student respondents from Indonesia and Malaysia.

The validity and Reliability Test is the first part of ensuring that each indicator used in the study is valid and reliable. The data used to analyze as many as three hundred data points that were successfully filled in and returned by respondents to the researcher.

The loading factor in SEM-PLS calculations is used to measure the validity of the indicators used in the study. If the loading factor value of an indicator is > 0.70 , it can be considered valid, and vice versa; if the loading factor value is less than 0.70, then the indicator needs to be removed from the model.

Table 2: Outer Loading Results

	Curriculum Content	Entrepreneurial Skills	Entrepreneurial Talent Development	Teaching Style	Results
X1.1				0,811	Valid
X1.2				0,823	Valid
X1.3				0,812	Valid

X2.1	0,837				Valid
X2.2	0,775				Valid
X2.3	0,866				Valid
X2.4	0,743				Valid
X3.1		0,790			Valid
X3.2		0,880			Valid
X3.3		0,865			Valid
X3.4		0,829			Valid
X3.5		0,845			Valid
X3.6		0,817			Valid
Y1			0,778		Valid
Y2			0,820		Valid
Y3			0,872		Valid
Y4			0,789		Valid

The opinion written by Hair et al, 2017 explains that if the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value is greater than 0.50, then it can be said that the variable can be said to be valid. The variables used in this study are Curriculum Content, Entrepreneurial Skills, Entrepreneurial Talent Development, and Teaching Style. The results show that the AVE value of the four variables above is > 0.50, which means that all variables used in the study are valid and reliable.

Table 3: Validity and Reliability Test Results

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Curriculum Content	0,823	0,833	0,881	0,651
Entrepreneurial Skills	0,915	0,916	0,934	0,703
Entrepreneurial Talent Development	0,832	0,836	0,888	0,665
Teaching Style	0,748	0,749	0,856	0,665

Inner Model Test

Table 4: R Square Test Results

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Entrepreneurial Skills	0,209	0,205
Entrepreneurial Talent Development	0,618	0,615

Based on the results of Table 4 above, the entrepreneurial skills variable gets an R-Square value of 0.209 or 20.9% (weak), which means that the product innovation variable does not have enough influence on Entrepreneurial Talent Development. In comparison, other factors outside this study influence the other 79.1%.

The Entrepreneurial Talent Development variable has an R-Square value of 0.618 or 61.8% (quite strong), which means that the curriculum content and teaching skills variables have a fairly strong influence on the Entrepreneurial Talent Development variable of 61.8%, and other factors outside this study influence the remaining 38.2%.

Hypothesis Test Results

Table 5: Hypothesis Test Results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Curriculum Content -> Entrepreneurial Skills (H1)	0,452	0,460	0,068	6,608	0,000
Curriculum Content -> Entrepreneurial Talent Development (H2)	0,369	0,369	0,064	5,730	0,000
Entrepreneurial Skills -> Entrepreneurial Talent Development (H3)	0,468	0,468	0,042	11,143	0,000
Teaching Style -> Entrepreneurial Skills (H4)	0,007	-0,002	0,072	0,103	0,918
Teaching Style -> Entrepreneurial Talent Development (H5)	0,109	0,111	0,060	1,804	0,072
Teaching Style -> Entrepreneurial Skills -> Entrepreneurial Talent Development (H6)	0,003	0,000	0,034	0,103	0,918
Curriculum Content -> Entrepreneurial Skills -> Entrepreneurial Talent Development (H7)	0,212	0,215	0,035	6,021	0,000

Overall, Table 6 provides answers to the hypotheses stated in the study. The results of the calculations that have been carried out show that hypotheses 1 to 3 have a positive and significant influence. Hypotheses 4 and 5 show that the impact is insignificant using $\alpha = 0.05$, but becomes significant at $\alpha = 0.10$, which means that the marginal influence needs to be studied further. While in hypothesis 6, using entrepreneurial skills as mediation, the results are not significant, in hypothesis 7, it is entrepreneurial skills that are the mediator for curriculum content and entrepreneurial talent development, the results are positive and essential.

DISCUSSION

1. The Influence of Curriculum Content on Entrepreneurial Skills

The table shows the path coefficient value: 0.452 (t-statistic = 6.608; p = 0.000), indicating a positive and significant influence. This study's results align with previous research conducted by Sirelkhatim and Ganggi (2015), which stated that Entrepreneurship education is one of the fastest-growing fields of education in the world. Various forms of learning and approaches to developing entrepreneurship education have always been a concern for many researchers to continue to be developed. The findings of previous studies that align with this study are those conducted by J Iqbalet al. (2022). The study stated that the learning environment on campus can mediate the relationship between the entrepreneurship curriculum, which contains curriculum content, curriculum materials, teaching strategies, and feedback and assessment, with entrepreneurial competencies. It can be said that well-designed curriculum content is fundamental in developing students' entrepreneurial skills. This study shows that the coefficient value of 0.452 indicates that every one-unit increase in the quality of curriculum content will increase entrepreneurial skills by 45.2%.

2. The Influence of Curriculum Content on Entrepreneurial Talent Development

The results in the table show a path coefficient value of 0.369 (t-statistic = 5.730; $p = 0.000$). These results strengthen the argument from previous studies, which state that curriculum content not only influences skill development but also directly affects the development of entrepreneurial talent. These results are in line with the writings of Anna Merod (2024) on how entrepreneurship curriculum needs to be developed by paying attention to creativity, digital literacy, critical thinking, collaboration, and persistence. Using the results of this study, the world of education is expected to create engaging curriculum content to help develop entrepreneurial talent in students.

3. The Influence of Entrepreneurial Skills on Entrepreneurial Talent Development

The study results on the 3rd hypothesis show the value of the path coefficient: 0.468 (t-statistic = 11.143; $p = 0.000$). This finding is one of the strongest in the proposed research model. These results indicate that entrepreneurial skills are the main predictor of developing entrepreneurial talent. The results of this study are supported by previous research conducted by Hermawan et al. (2024), who stated that entrepreneurial cognition and skills can be the primary mediators and moderators between entrepreneurship education and the development of entrepreneurial competencies for everyone who studies it.

4. The Influence of Teaching Style on Entrepreneurial Skills

The results obtained in this fourth hypothesis show surprising or different findings compared to previous research conducted by Esmi K. *et al.* (2015), who stated that teaching style directly influences the acceptance of entrepreneurial material to improve entrepreneurial skills. Although the research results are shown through the value **Path coefficient: 0.007** (t-statistic = 0.103; $p = 0.918$), the result is that there is no significant influence, namely that the teaching style directly does not have a substantial effect on the development of entrepreneurial skills. This can happen because a teacher's teaching style may depend on the context and suitability of the curriculum content used.

5. The Influence of Teaching Style on Entrepreneurial Talent Development

The study showed no significant effect when using $\alpha = 0.05$, but the results showed a substantial impact at $\alpha = 0.10$, by looking at the Path Coefficient value: 0.109 (t-statistic = 1.804; $p = 0.072$). The p-value = 0.072 indicates a probability of 7.2%, which means that the observed effect occurs by chance using the hypothesis proposed in the study. This result is supported by Lackeus's research (2015), which states that the effect of teaching style on entrepreneurship outcomes is not always consistent. This can occur because of the complexity of the relationship between teaching methods and the results of entrepreneurship teaching.

6. Mediation Effect of Teaching Style → Entrepreneurial Skills → Entrepreneurial Talent Development

The study results showed a very low mediation coefficient (0.003) with t-statistic = 0.103 and $p = 0.918$, indicating no significant mediation effect between Teaching Style and Entrepreneurial Talent Development through Entrepreneurial Skills.

The p -value = 0.918 indicates a 91.8% probability that the observed effect occurs by chance. This may occur due to several of the following reasons: the measured teaching style may not be by the needs of entrepreneurial skills development, the teaching style construct may be too general so that it cannot capture relevant specific aspects, and the last is contextual factors that may have a greater influence than the teaching style itself.

7. Curriculum Content → Entrepreneurial Skills → Entrepreneurial Talent Development

The study showed a significant mediation effect with a coefficient of 0.212 (t -statistic = 6.021; $p = 0.000$). This finding indicates that entrepreneurial skills have a strong role as a mediator in the relationship between curriculum content and entrepreneurial talent development. The t -statistic value > 1.96 and $p < 0.001$ indicate a very high statistical significance relationship. The coefficient value of 0.212 shows that 21.2% of the influence of curriculum content on entrepreneurial talent development occurs through the development of entrepreneurial skills experienced by the research respondents.

This result states that there is a substantial mediation effect in the context of entrepreneurship education. The results of this study align with previous research conducted by Ake et al. (2022), which shows that curriculum content has an important role as a predictor in the development of entrepreneurial skills. This study is also in line with the findings of research conducted by Yue et al. (2023); the results strengthen the argument that skills are a connecting mechanism between educational input and talent development outcomes in entrepreneurship.

CONCLUSION AND MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Based on the analysis and discussion results, this study produces several key findings that focus on the context of entrepreneurial talent development through entrepreneurship education. The following is a summary of the research results:

1. Dominance of Curriculum Content in Entrepreneurship Development

The results of the study can provide evidence that curriculum content is one of the most crucial factors in the development of entrepreneurial skills and talents, as shown by the results of the path coefficient of 0.452 on entrepreneurial skills and 0.369 on entrepreneurial talent development, this states that curriculum content shows a consistent and significant influence. This finding confirms that "what is taught" is more important than "how to teach it"; this result applies to entrepreneurship education.

2. Significant Role of Entrepreneurial Skills Mediation

The study results indicate that entrepreneurial skills are a very effective mediator in the relationship between curriculum content and entrepreneurial talent development (mediation coefficient = 0.212; $p = 0.000$). This figure states that 21.2% of the influence of curriculum content on entrepreneurial talent development can occur through the development of entrepreneurial skills. This result also indicates the existence of a systematic transformation pathway from knowledge to skills, which can then develop into entrepreneurial talent.

3. Limitations of Teaching Style in the Context of Entrepreneurship

The study also provided surprising results, namely that the minimal influence of teaching style on the development of entrepreneurial skills and talents, as indicated by very low coefficient values (0.007 and 0.109), also showed no significant mediation effect. The study results conclude that conventional teaching styles may be less appropriate to the needs of practical and experiential entrepreneurial learning.

4. Hierarchy of Influence in Talent Development Model

The results of this study reveal findings related to a clear hierarchy of influence on the relationship between Entrepreneurial Skills → Entrepreneurial Talent Development (coefficient = 0.468) is the strongest relationship in the model, followed by Curriculum Content → Entrepreneurial Skills (coefficient = 0.452). These results explain that the development of entrepreneurial talent generally follows a systematic and predictable path.

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

This research produces several recommendations as new research results and as part of managerial implications.

- Educational institutions can focus more on curriculum development to improve entrepreneurship education, which impacts the formation of entrepreneurial character for their students.
- The government, especially the Department of Education, can create policies regarding developing an entrepreneurship curriculum that can be applied from elementary, secondary, to higher education, aiming to build entrepreneurial talent early on.
- This research is expected to be an evidence-based roadmap for optimizing entrepreneurship education. Educational institutions can create a sustainable competitive advantage by focusing on curriculum content quality and systematic skills development to produce graduates ready to become successful entrepreneurs or intrapreneurs.
- The research results also stated that optimizing investment to develop entrepreneurial content and skills provides significant returns in the form of quality entrepreneurial talent.
- Higher education institutions need to transform traditional teaching approaches so that the results of entrepreneurship learning can achieve optimal results for students.

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